

Relevance of Albumin as Prognostic Marker in Orthopaedic Trauma Elderly Patients

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Abstract:

After surgery, there could be reduced albumin production in the liver or increased albumin breakdown. In both cases, the level of serum albumin decreases. Stress and strain are also recognized factors contributing to hypoalbuminemia, which refers to low serum albumin levels. Albumin, being a protein, is synthesized from genetic transcription, and research indicates that TNF-alpha inhibits this transcription process.

Keywords: Albumin, Prognosis, Hospitalized, Surgery, Patients.

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Introduction

The normal serum level found in healthy adults typically ranges from three to five grams per deciliter. Levels below two grams per deciliter are considered low. Reduced albumin formation in the liver or increased albumin degradation can lead to hypoalbuminemia in pathological conditions [1]. Stress and strain have also been associated with low serum albumin levels [2,3]. Since albumin is a protein, its synthesis is regulated by gene transcription, which studies have shown can be suppressed by TNF-alpha [4,5,6]. TNF-alpha levels typically rise during inflammation, contributing to a cascade effect.

In hospitalized patients, particularly those undergoing surgery or experiencing chronic hospitalization, serum albumin levels are frequently below normal. Nutritional deficiencies are also a potential cause of decreased serum albumin in chronically hospitalized patients. Early detection of low serum albumin levels enables prompt intervention by physicians and surgeons, potentially halting disease progression [7-11].

This study aims to investigate the relationship between serum albumin levels and disease prognosis, as well as surgical outcomes. The findings seek to provide valuable insights for healthcare professionals, including physicians, surgeons, and general practitioners, facilitating earlier and more effective patient recovery. Southampton wound scoring system used for assessment of wound condition in this study

Aims and Objective:

1. To establish a role of serum albumin with patient's prognosis.

Method:

The research was conducted at the Department of Orthopedics, S.R.G Hospital And Medical College, Jhalawar, spanning from May 2023 To May 2024. The study involved a sample size of two hundred patients identified in the orthopedic department. Serum albumin levels were measured, and the hospitalized patients were categorized into two groups:

Group 1- No albumin administered

Group 2- Albumin administered

Group 2a – preoperatively albumin administered

Group 2b – albumin administered on post operative day 2

Subsequently, serum albumin levels were re-assessed, and patient prognosis was evaluated based on factors such as non-wound healing, symptom exacerbation, intraoperative complications, post-operative sepsis, and mortality. Each group received appropriate treatment, including nutritional supplementation, and their prognosis was monitored. Serum albumin levels were again measured, and prognosis was assessed in terms of non-wound healing, pain management, and mortality.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All elderly patients (>60year) having trochanteric and neck of femur fractures with albumin level less than 3.5g/dl

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients receiving medications associated with decreased serum albumin levels.

2. Chronic liver illness.

Results:

Table 1: Occurrence of patients within each segmented category

Groups	Number of Patients
Group 1	100
Group 2a	50
Group 2b (albumin administered on post operative day 2)	50

Table 2: Analysis of Prognostic Table in Relation to albumin administration.

Groups	Prognosis
Group 1 (no albumin administered)	Discharge from suture line- 70 Pain-80 Intrasurgical complications-40 Post operative sepsis-15 Death-5
Group 2 (albumin administered)	Discharge from suture line-28 Pain-45 Intrasurgical complications-18 Post operative sepsis-4 Death-0
Group 2a (preoperatively albumin administered)	Discharge from suture line-10 Pain-20 Intrasurgical complications-8 Post operative sepsis-1 Death-0
Group 2b (albumin administered on post operative day 2)	Discharge from suture line-18 Pain-25 Intrasurgical complications-10 Post operative sepsis-3 Death-0

Table 3: Serum Albumin Levels in Patients Post-Correction

Groups	Mean serum albumin level
Group 1 (no albumin administered)	2.9
Group 2a (preoperatively albumin administered)	4.2
Group 2b (albumin given on post operative day 2)	3.9

Table 4a: Table of Significance

Groups	Prognosis	P value
Group 1 (no albumin administered)	Discharge from suture line	0.0001
	Pain	0.0001
Group 2a (preoperatively albumin administered)	Intrasurgical complication	0.0025
	Post operative sepsis	0.0235
Group 2b(albumin given on post operative day 2)	Death	0.0235

Table 4b: Table of Significance

Groups	Prognosis	P value
Group 1 (no albumin administered)	Discharge from suture line	0.0001
	Pain	0.0002
	Intrasurgical complication	0.0006
Group 2 (albumin administered)	Post operative sepsis	0.007
	Death	0.0235

Southampton Wound Scoring System

Grade	Appearance
0	Normal healing
	Normal healing with mild bruising or erythema
I	I a Some bruising
	I b Considerable bruising
	I c Mild erythema
	Erythema plus other signs of inflammation
II	II a At one point
	II b Around sutures
	II c Along wound
	II d Around wound
	Clear or haemoserous discharge
III	III a At one point only (≤ 2 cm)
	III b Along wound (>2 cm)
	III c Large volume
	III d Prolonged (> 3 days)
	Pus
IV	IV a At one point only (≤ 2 cm)
	IV b Along wound (>2 cm)
V	Deep or severe wound infection with or without tissue breakdown; hematoma requiring aspiration

Table 4: Southampton wound scoring table

Groups	No. of Patients	Wound Score
Group 1	50	Score 0
	24	Score 1
	24	Score 2
	5	Score 3
	1	Score 4
	1	Score 5
	Group 2a	40
08		Score 1
02		Score 2
00		Score 3
00		Score 4
00		Score 5
Group 2b	30	Score 0
	15	Score 1
	04	Score 2
	01	Score 3
	00	Score 4
	00	Score 5

Clinical Photos

Post-Operative Day 2 Dressing Photo
(Group 1 Patient)

[Discharge Present]

Post-Operative Day-5 Dressing Photo
(Group 1 Patient)
[Still Discharge Present]

Post-Operative Day-2 Dressing Photo
(Group 2 Patient)
[Redness Present Over Stitch Line]

Post-Operative Day-5 Dressing Photo**(Group 2 Patient)****[No Redness Over Stitch Line]****Discussion**

The findings of this study align with previous research conducted by Luiz Ronaldo Alberti, Andy Petroianu(10), and Donald A Redelmeier.(11)

Albumin serves as a crucial transport protein, facilitating the carriage of hydrophobic substances that are not water-soluble. It functions as both a binding agent and a carrier protein, aiding in the transportation of essential hydrophobic drugs with significant pharmacodynamic effects. Moreover, albumin plays a vital role in lipid metabolism by transporting fatty acids and aiding in the metabolism of bile salts and acids. Due to its charged nature, albumin can be effectively excreted by the kidneys. Disruption of this charge balance can lead to nephrotic syndrome, particularly common in children, although it tends to be a self-limiting condition. Additionally, albumin contributes to the maintenance of colloidal osmotic pressure, preventing the leakage of serum into tissue spaces and thus mitigating the development of edema, a characteristic manifestation of low albumin levels.

Many experts attribute adverse outcomes in diseases and surgeries to low albumin levels. Reduced albumin can lead to edema, hindering the effectiveness of antibiotics in reaching the affected area of the body. Additionally, low albumin levels

may disrupt the normal metabolic pathways of various drugs. These factors must be carefully considered when planning treatment schedules. Pre-surgical correction of albumin levels can have significant benefits for patients, particularly those undergoing surgical procedures. Improved prognosis is often observed in patients with normalized serum albumin levels compared to those with low levels.

Conclusion:

The current study highlights a notable variance in patient prognosis corresponding to increases in serum albumin levels and this conclusion is signified by obtained p values.

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